

Short communication

First record of *Eurydema dominulus* (Scopoli, 1763) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Pentatomidae) for Greece

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Abstract. The first record of *Eurydema (Rubrodorsalium) dominulus* (Scopoli, 1763) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Pentatomidae: Pentatominae) for Greece is reported. The European distribution of the species is summarised. Furthermore, the known species of the genus *Eurydema* Laporte de Castelnau, 1833 in Greece are listed.

Key words: Heteroptera, Pentatomidae, *Eurydema dominulus*, distribution, new record, Europe, Greece.

Up to now, nine species of the genus *Eurydema* Laporte de Castelnau, 1833 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Pentatomidae: Pentatominae) have been reported for Greece: *Eurydema (Eurydema) eckerleini* Josifov, 1961, *E. (E.) oleracea* (Linnaeus, 1758), *E. (E.) ornata* (Linnaeus, 1758), *E. (Horvatheurydema) fieberi* Fieber, 1837, *E. (H.) rotundicollis* (Dohrn, 1860), *E. (H.) rugulosa* (Dohrn, 1860), *E. (Rubrodorsalium) blanda* Horváth, 1903, *E. (R.) spectabilis* Horváth, 1882 and *E. (R.) ventralis* Kolenati, 1846 (Ramsay 2019; Tsagkarakis et al. 2022).

Eurydema (Rubrodorsalium) dominulus (Scopoli, 1763) has been reported from the following European countries, so far: Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, the Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Moldavia, Montenegro, the Netherlands, North Macedonia, Poland, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland and Ukraine (Protić 2016; Aukema 2024).

Greece can be added to the list of the distribution of *E. dominulus*: On 02.09.2018, Kostas Zontanos observed the species in the Verno mountain range between Florina and Kastoria, located in Western Macedonia (Fig. 1). Three related photos were uploaded to the online platform iNaturalist (Zontanos 2018).

As *E. dominulus* has not been reported from Greece in scientific publications yet, this is the first record of the species for the country.

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Fig. 1. Specimen of *Eurydema (Rubrodorsalium) dominulus* (Scopoli, 1763), Verno mountain range between Florina and Kastoria, Greece (photo: Kostas Zontanos).

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